

Multiwavelength variability of high energy AGN: the case of NGC 2110

Francesca Panessa

AGN PHYSICS and FEEDBACK MAIN PLAYERS:

Maiolino et al. 2017 - Image credit: ESO / M. Kornmesser

- Accretion disc
- Hot corona
- Wind
- Jet
- Star-formation

→ Radio and X-rays emitters!

AGN: WITH JETS, WITHOUT JETS

With jet:

- ✓ Large scale radio lobes
- ✓ Compact luminous cores often with apparent luminal motions

Radio Loud

Without jet:

- ✓ Faint radio sources
- ✓ Emission confined to sub-kpc scale

Radio Quiet

RADIO LOUDNESS

$$R = L(5 \text{ GHz}) / L(B)$$

➤ MULTI-FREQUENCY

➤ MULTI SCALE

WINDS

➤ MULTI-FREQUENCY

➤ MULTI SCALE

JETS

JETS and WINDS interplay

How are jets and winds formed?

Are they a phase of the AGN life?

Is the jet and the wind connected to the accretion flow and how?

Does the disk wind collimate the jet?

How is the jet and wind feedback acting in galaxies?

Magneto-hydrodynamic models
(Tchekhovskoy et al. 2011, Fukumura et al. 2014)

Meyer-Hofmeister et al. 2009

THE RADIO and X-RAY SYNERGY

The radio emission in RQ AGN

Origin of Radio Emission in RADIO QUIET AGN

Panessa, Baldi, Laor, Padovani, Behar & McHardy 2019, Nature Astronomy Review

VARIABILITY

JETTED AGN

Simplified SED of a blazar.

RADIO VARIABILITY in JETTED AGN

Radio VARIABILITY in RADIO QUIET AGN

Radio VARIABILITY in RADIO QUIET AGN

Typical variability of 10-20%

Wrobel 2000 ; Anderson & Ulvestad 2005 ; Barvainis et al. 2005 ; Mundell et al. 2009 ; Bell et al. 2011 ;
Doi, Asada & Nagai 2011 ; King et al. 2013 ; Baldi et al. 2015 ; Behar et al. 2020 ; Williams et al. 2020

NGC 2110 Overview

- Nearby ($z=0.0076$) Seyfert 2
 - Complex structure at different spatial scales
 - Warm H_2 inflow and outflow (Dinz et al. 2015)
- feeding and feedback (Scnorr-Muller et al. 2014)

HARD X-ray EMISSION of NGC 2110

Ursini et al. 2019

- Hard X-ray variable emission (flare-like?)

Ronchini et al. in preparation

- High energy cut-off of 320 (+100; -60) keV (Ursini et al. 2019)
- Variable partial-covering absorber (Evans et al. 2017)

RADIO EMISSION of NGC 2110

- S-shaped radio emission → Radio Galaxy
- Compact core
- Strong Variability (Mundell et al. 2009)

VARIABLE RADIO EMISSION of NGC 2110

- Core Variability at
 - 8.4 GHz of 61% over 8 years
 - 5 GHz of 69% over 12 years
 - 15 GHz of 24% over 2 years

A TRANSITION/INTERMEDIATE AGN: NGC 2110

RADIO QUIET → low radio – loudness
parameter – low power core

RADIO LOUD → two pair of lobes FR II-like

S-SHAPE radio lobes:

- interaction with a rotating ISM
- precessing jet (origin of variability?)
- radio emission of jet origin (no excess at mm band as expected from a corona)

Either a **transition** object from RL to RQ
or
an **intermediate** source

Radio VARIABILITY in RADIO QUIET AGN

AMI 15 GHz Light Curves of INTEGRAL Hard X-ray selected AGN

- All of them DO VARY
- Variability fractions 10-60%

Radio VARIABILITY in RADIO QUIET AGN

- RADIO QUIET AGN are VARIABLE in the RADIO
- New tool for the study of AGN physics

- **NEW CLASSES:**
 - **CHANGING LOOK AGN**
 - **TDE-like AGN**
 - **FLARING RQ AGN**

Thank you

